

“Knowledge should be freely available.”

Jean-Paul Faguet, Professor
of the Political Economy of
Development at London School of
Economics and Political Science

Academics working for wealthy institutions in the Global North don't always realise the access issues facing academics working for less wealthy institutions, particularly those in the Global South.

Faguet says open access publishing helps address issues of inequality, which he feels is particularly important in his area of research. He wouldn't like to be conducting fieldwork and gathering data and then putting it all behind a paywall where only those at elite institutions in the Global North can access it.

“The people we study live in developing countries, and the results, conclusions and recommendations – the main point of this research – is really aimed at developing countries, first and foremost.”

Why Faguet believes in open access publishing

Research reaches people who need it

Knowledge is shared equitably around the world

Data and evidence can be used for the greater good

It stops research from being extractive